

Square-Waves Driving a Low-Pass Filter

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Abstract

The purpose of this paper is to derive the mathematical equations describing unipolar and symmetric bipolar square-waves of arbitrary duty cycle, and the steady state response of a first order low-pass filter to these square-waves. We first consider the unipolar square-wave and then, using two methods, the symmetrical bipolar square-wave. Laplace transforms are employed.

The results are useful in, among other applications, the design modeling and computer simulation of primary coil excitation of magnetic flux-gates.

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1 Introduction: The First Order Low-Pass Filter

We review derivations of and solutions to simple first-order ordinary differential equations involving the 1st order low-pass filter as used in simple electrical circuits. Solutions to the differential equation using both, the "classical" and Laplace transform methods are considered and compared. Finally, for the square-wave input signals which we address in this paper, Laplace transforms are mathematically probably more tractable and are used here.

We then consider the steady state response (output) of such a circuit, that is, the response as $t \rightarrow \infty$. We do this by subtracting the transient term from the complete solution. There are two ways to accomplish this. We can obtain the inverse Laplace transform and subtract from it the transient terms. Alternatively, we can take the original Laplace transform and subtract from it the Laplace transform of the transient solution. The result will be the Laplace transform of the steady state.

The Laplace Transform Method

$$\tau \dot{y} + y = x(t), \quad \dot{y} + \frac{1}{\tau}y = \frac{1}{\tau}x(t) \quad \text{or} \quad \dot{y} + \Omega y = \Omega x(t)$$

In this differential equation, $x(t)$ is the effort variable, typically the voltage driving the circuit. y is the flow variable, typically a voltage measured across a resistor R , a capacitor C , or an inductor L . The time constant is $\tau = \tau(t)$ and $\Omega = \frac{1}{\tau}$. The initial condition is $y(0)$.

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{L}(\tau \dot{y} + y) &= \mathcal{L}x(t) \quad \text{or} \quad \mathcal{L}(\dot{y} + \Omega y) = \mathcal{L}\Omega x(t) \\ \tau \mathcal{L}\dot{y} + \mathcal{L}y &= \mathcal{L}x(t)\end{aligned}$$

But $\mathcal{L}\dot{y}(t) = sY(s) - Y(0)$ or $\mathcal{L}\dot{y}(t) = sy(s) - y(0)$

So

$$\begin{aligned}\tau [sy(s) - y(0)] + y(s) &= x(s) \\ y(s) &= \frac{x(s)}{\tau s + 1} + \frac{\tau y(0)}{\tau s + 1} \quad \text{or} \quad y(s) = \frac{\Omega x(s)}{s + \Omega} + \frac{y(0)}{s + \Omega}\end{aligned}$$

$$\boxed{y(t) = \Omega \mathcal{L}^{-1} \frac{x(s)}{s + \Omega} + y(0) e^{-\Omega t}} \quad (1)$$

This is the complete solution to the differential equation, i.e., it includes the transient portions. Laplace transforms are usually ill suited for determining the solutions of linear differential equations with variable coefficients (non-constant Ω). We consider only constant Ω here, i.e., linear time-invariant systems. For variable coefficients we rely on the classic method of obtaining solutions.

The first term on the right represents the forced response of the system. The second term on the right represents part of the transient response of the system. We have taken the liberty above of using the same kernel symbol x (rather than, say, X) to represent the time function and Laplace transform, distinguishing one from the other by use of independent variable t or s . Typically in Laplace transform usage, $y(0) = 0$. Thus, that part of the transient response is removed. (This is the equivalent of simply ignoring it). The forced response for periodic square-wave inputs into a lowpass filter *LPF1* typically includes an additional transient component, as the system adjusts to its steady state. The initial value of $y(t)$ at the beginning of a half-cycle is equal to the final value at the end of the previous half-cycle.

For example: Consider a unit step function $x(t) = \sigma(t)$ input to a 1st order lowpass filter *LPF1*.

Using the "classic" method to solve the differential equation with constant Ω , $\int \Omega dt = \Omega t$ and

$$y(t) = e^{\int -\Omega dt} \left(\int \Omega \sigma(t) e^{\int \Omega dt} dt + C \right) \quad (2)$$

$$y(t) = e^{-\Omega t} \Omega \left(\int e^{\Omega t} dt + C \right) = e^{-\Omega t} (e^{\Omega t} + C) = 1 + C e^{-\Omega t}$$

Initial condition

$$y(0) = 0 \quad \Rightarrow \quad y(0) = 0 = 1 + C \quad \Rightarrow \quad C = y(0) - 1$$

$$\therefore y(t) = 1 + [(y(0) - 1)] e^{-\Omega t} = (1 - e^{-\Omega t}) + y(0) e^{-\Omega t}$$

Similarly, but this time using the Laplace transform method to solve the differential equation, with $x(s) = \frac{1}{s}$ and $\Omega = \frac{1}{\tau}$,

$$y(s) = \frac{1}{s} \frac{1}{\tau s + 1} + \frac{\tau y(0)}{\tau s + 1} = \frac{\Omega}{s(s + \Omega)} + \frac{y(0)}{s + \Omega}$$

$$y(t) = \mathcal{L}^{-1} \left[\frac{\Omega}{s(s + \Omega)} + \frac{y(0)}{s + \Omega} \right] = (1 - e^{-\Omega t}) \sigma(t) + y(0) e^{-\Omega t}$$

which is in agreement with the solution obtained via the classical method. As previously discussed, we set $y(0) = 0$.

Notice in this example that the forced response term $(1 - e^{-\Omega t})$ contains a transient component $-e^{-\Omega t}$ as well as a steady state component 1. We shall further consider this shortly.

The *LPF1 system* Laplace transform is $\frac{1}{s + \Omega}$ and the *input signal* Laplace transform is $\frac{1}{s}$.

"Transient" term: In the forced response, there is a pole at $s = -\Omega$ in the *system* Laplace transform. Therefore, set $s = -\Omega$ in the *input signal* Laplace transform. The transient component $y_t(t)$ of the forced response term $y(t)$ is

$$y_t(s) = \frac{\Omega}{(-\Omega)(s + \Omega)} = -\frac{1}{s + \Omega}$$

$$\Rightarrow y_t(t) = \mathcal{L}^{-1} y_t(s) = -e^{-\Omega t} = -e^{-t/\tau}$$

$$y(t) = y_{ss}(t) + y_t(t) \quad \Rightarrow \quad y_{ss}(t) = y(t) - y_t(t)$$

$$\therefore y_{ss}(t) = (1 - e^{-\Omega t}) \sigma(t) - (-e^{-\Omega t}) = 1$$

as expected, where $y_{ss}(t)$ is the steady-state response term of the solution.

We will later employ the same kind of reasoning when considering the steady-state response of the low-pass filter to square waves.

2 Unipolar SquareWave Driving a Low-Pass Filter

(Displayed: Three cycles with Duty Cycle $d = 0.5$)

Figure 1: A Unipolar Square-wave

Let $f(t)$ (or SQWV1(t)) be a periodic unipolar square-wave of amplitude 1 and (arbitrary) duty cycle $d = \frac{t_{HI}}{t_{HI} + t_{LO}} = \frac{t_{HI}}{T}$. The period of the square-wave is $T = t_{HI} + t_{LO}$. We address the form of this function in the next sub-section. Let the excitation voltage driving a low-pass filter $LPF1(s) = \frac{1}{\tau s + 1}$ be $\varphi = \varphi_0 f(t) = \begin{cases} \varphi_0, & t < dT \\ 0, & t \geq dT \end{cases}$ with amplitude $\varphi_0 > 0$.

Example circuits:

If we have a capacitor C in series with a resistor R , the transfer function for the output voltage across the capacitor is $\varphi_c(t) = \varphi LPF1(\tau)$, that is, $\varphi_c(t) = \varphi \frac{1}{\tau D + 1}$ and $\tau = RC$ is the system time constant.

Similarly, if we have coil of constant inductance L in series with a resistor R , the transfer function for current (the output) through the RL string is $i(t) = \frac{\varphi}{R} LPF1(\tau)$, that is, $i(t) = \frac{\varphi}{R} \frac{1}{\tau D + 1}$ and $\tau = \frac{L}{R}$ is the system time constant.

$LPF1(t) = \frac{1}{\tau D + 1}$ is the low-pass filter operator and $D = \frac{d}{dt}$ is the differential operator with respect to time.

First, consider the *first cycle* $f_0(t)$ of the unipolar square-wave.

$$f_0(t) = \sigma(t) - \sigma(t - dT)$$

This waveform must be replicated with time period T to form $f(t)$.

$$f(t) = \sigma(t) - \sigma(t - dT) + \sigma(t - T) - \sigma[t - (1 + d)T] + \sigma(t - 2T) - \sigma[t - (2 + d)T] + \dots + etc.$$

$$\text{that is, } f(t) = \begin{cases} +1, & t \in [kT, (k + d)T) \\ 0, & t \in [(k + d)T, kT) \end{cases}, \text{ integer } k \in [0, \infty)$$

$$f(t) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} [\sigma(t - kT) - \sigma[t - (k + d)T]] \quad (3)$$

Let $\Phi_i(s) = \mathcal{L}(\varphi(t)) = \mathcal{L}[\varphi_0 f(t)] = \varphi_0 \mathcal{L}f(t) = \varphi_0 F(s)$,

the Laplace transform of the unipolar square-wave function of voltage input of amplitude φ_0 into the low-pass filter *LPF1*.

2.1 Digression

Suppose that $x(t)$ is a periodic function with period T . Let $x_0(t)$ be the first period component function

$$x_0(t) = \begin{cases} x(t), & t \in [0, T) \\ 0, & \text{elsewhere} \end{cases} = \sigma(t) - \sigma(t - dT)$$

and $X_0(s)$ be its Laplace transform.

$$x(t) = x_0(t) + x_0(t - T) + x_0(t - 2T) + \dots + \text{etc.} = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} x_0(t - kT)$$

$$X(s) = \mathcal{L}x(t) = X_0(s) + e^{-Ts} X_0(s) + e^{-2Ts} X_0(s) + \dots + \text{etc.}$$

$$X(s) = X_0(s) (1 + e^{-Ts} + e^{-2Ts} + \dots + \text{etc.}) = X_0(s) \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} e^{-kTs} = X_0(s) \frac{1}{1 - e^{-Ts}} \quad (4)$$

With $x_0(t) = \sigma(t) - \sigma(t - dT)$,

$$X_0(s) = \mathcal{L}[\sigma(t) - \sigma(t - dT)] = \frac{1}{s} - \frac{1}{s} e^{-dT s} = \frac{1}{s} (1 - e^{-dT s})$$

$$\therefore \boxed{X(s) = \frac{1}{s} \frac{1 - e^{-dT s}}{1 - e^{-Ts}}} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Iff } d = 0.5, \quad X(s) = \frac{1}{s} \frac{1 - e^{-Ts/2}}{(1 - e^{-Ts/2})(1 + e^{-Ts/2})} = \frac{1}{s(1 + e^{-Ts/2})}$$

The *repetition operator* is $RPT(s) \stackrel{D}{=} \frac{1}{1 - e^{-Ts}}$, and so for a unipolar square-wave SQWV(t) of amplitude 1 and period T ,

$$X(s) = \mathcal{L} \text{SQWV}(t) = \frac{1}{s} RPT(s) = \frac{1}{s(1 + e^{-Ts})}.$$

End of Digression.

Now consider the coil of constant inductance L in series with the resistor R . Time constant $\tau = L/R$ and $\Omega = 1/\tau$. The Laplace transform of the square-wave voltage input to the low-pass filter *LPF1* is

$$\Phi_i(s) = \frac{\varphi_0}{s} \frac{1 - e^{-dT_s}}{1 - e^{-Ts}}$$

The output voltage (across resistor R) of the low-pass filter $LPF1$ is

$$\boxed{\Phi_o(s) = \Phi_i(s) LPF1(s) = \frac{\varphi_0}{s} \frac{1 - e^{-dT_s}}{1 - e^{-Ts}} \frac{\Omega}{s + \Omega}} \quad (6)$$

and the current through the RL string is $I_o(s) = \frac{\Phi_o(s)}{R}$. We may then determine $i_o(t) = \mathcal{L}^{-1} I_o(s)$.

2.2 Removing the Transient Term

There is a pole at $s = -\Omega$ in the input signal Laplace transform. Replacing all occurrences of s by $-\Omega$ in $\Phi_o(s)$, we obtain the transient term...

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_t(s) &= \frac{\varphi_0}{(-\Omega)} \frac{1 - e^{d\Omega T}}{1 - e^{\Omega T}} \frac{\Omega}{s + \Omega} \\ &= -\varphi_0 \left(\frac{1 - e^{d\Omega T}}{1 - e^{\Omega T}} \right) \frac{1}{s + \Omega} \end{aligned}$$

or

$$\boxed{\Phi_t(s) = -\varphi_0 \frac{C_1}{s + \Omega} \text{ in which } C_1 \stackrel{D}{=} \frac{1 - e^{d\Omega T}}{1 - e^{\Omega T}} \text{ and } C_1 > 0} \quad (7)$$

$$\text{Also, } C_1 = \frac{e^{-\Omega T} (1 - e^{d\Omega T})}{e^{-\Omega T} (1 - e^{\Omega T})} = -\frac{e^{-\Omega T} - e^{-(1-d)\Omega T}}{1 - e^{-\Omega T}}$$

Note the signs on the exponents. So,

$$\varphi_t(t) = -\varphi_0 C_1 e^{-\Omega t} \quad (8)$$

Steady state solution = Complete solution - Transient solution

The steady state term $\Phi(s) = \Phi_o(s) - \Phi_t(s)$.

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi(s) &= \frac{\varphi_0}{s} \frac{1 - e^{-dT_s}}{1 - e^{-Ts}} \frac{\Omega}{s + \Omega} - \left(-\frac{\varphi_0}{\Omega} C_1 \frac{\Omega}{s + \Omega} \right) \\ \Phi(s) &= \frac{\varphi_0}{s(s + \Omega)} \left[\frac{\Omega (1 - e^{-dT_s})}{1 - e^{-Ts}} + s C_1 \right] \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

$$\Phi(s) = \frac{\varphi_0}{s(s+\Omega)} \left[\frac{\Omega(1-e^{-dT_s})}{1-e^{-Ts}} + sC_1 \frac{1-e^{-Ts}}{1-e^{-Ts}} \right]$$

$$\Phi(s) = \frac{\varphi_0}{s(s+\Omega)(1-e^{-Ts})} [\Omega(1-e^{-dT_s}) + sC_1(1-e^{-Ts})]$$

2.3 Removing the Periodic Replication

$\Phi(s)$ is the Laplace transform of the *steady state* response for all cycles, $k = 0$ to ∞ . But we are only interested in the first cycle of the steady state (as $t \rightarrow \infty$, they are all the same; the $\Phi(s)$ above is the Laplace transform for all of the steady-state cycles). Recall that the factor $\frac{1}{1-e^{-Ts}}$ replicates the first cycle of the steady state response. Therefore, we simply replace it by 1, i.e., $\frac{1}{1-e^{-Ts}} \leftarrow 1$. Similarly, e^{-Ts} is a delay, which is not needed when considering one cycle of the steady state; so, $e^{-Ts} \leftarrow 0$. We dropped all remaining term containing the factor e^{-Ts} , but not e^{-dT_s} , since that corresponds to a one-half cycle delay.

Hence, for one cycle of the steady state response,

$$\Phi(s) = \frac{\varphi_0}{s(s+\Omega)} [\Omega(1-e^{-dT_s}) + C_1 s] \quad (10)$$

Rearranging terms and splitting them into two parts, the complete one-cycle steady state response of the system is...

$$\boxed{\Phi(s) = \frac{\varphi_0}{s(s+\Omega)} [(\Omega + C_1 s) - \Omega e^{-dT_s}] = \Phi_1(s) + \Phi_2(s)} \quad (11)$$

wherein which

$$\Phi_1(s) = \frac{\varphi_0}{s(s+\Omega)} (\Omega + C_1 s) \quad (12)$$

and

$$\Phi_2(s) = -\varphi_0 \frac{\Omega}{s(s+\Omega)} e^{-dT_s} \quad (13)$$

As we shall see after obtaining the inverse Laplace transforms of these two equations, $\Phi_1(s)$ is the system response during $t < dT$ due to the 1st half-cycle of excitation, and

$\Phi_2(s)$ is the *additional* system response during $t \geq dT$ due to the 2nd half-cycle of excitation. That is, this 2nd half-cycle excitation $\Phi_2(s)$ is augmented by the sustained contribution of response from the 1st half-cycle which persists into the 2nd half-cycle. Thus, the system response during $t \geq dT$ is $\Phi_1(s) + \Phi_2(s)$.

We now determine, step by step, the inverse Laplace transform of each of these two terms.

2.3.1 First Half-Cycle

$$\begin{aligned}\varphi_1(t) &= \mathcal{L}^{-1} \left[\frac{\varphi_0}{s(s+\Omega)} (\Omega + C_1 s) \right] \\ \varphi_1(t) &= \varphi_0 \mathcal{L}^{-1} \frac{\Omega}{s(s+\Omega)} + \varphi_0 C_1 \mathcal{L}^{-1} \frac{1}{s+\Omega} \\ \varphi_1(t) &= \varphi_0 (1 - e^{-\Omega t}) \sigma(t) + \varphi_0 C_1 e^{-\Omega t} \sigma(t)\end{aligned}\tag{14}$$

Rearranging terms,

$$\varphi_1(t) = \varphi_0 [1 - (1 - C_1) e^{-\Omega t}] \sigma(t)\tag{15}$$

and noting that $C_2 = 1 - C_1$,

$$\boxed{\varphi_1(t) = \varphi_0 (1 - C_2 e^{-\frac{t}{\tau}}) \sigma(t)} \quad \text{where} \quad \boxed{C_2 \stackrel{D}{=} -\frac{e^{\Omega T} - e^{d\Omega T}}{1 - e^{\Omega T}} = \frac{e^{d\Omega T} - e^{\Omega T}}{1 - e^{\Omega T}}}\tag{16}$$

or

$$C_2 = \frac{e^{-\Omega T}}{e^{-\Omega T}} \left(-\frac{e^{\Omega T} - e^{d\Omega T}}{1 - e^{\Omega T}} \right) = \frac{1 - e^{-(1-d)\Omega T}}{1 - e^{-\Omega T}} \quad \text{and} \quad C_2 > 0$$

We observe that due to the presence of $\sigma(t)$ in the $\varphi_1(t)$ equation above, the signal $\varphi_1(t)$ persists into the the 2^{nd} half-cycle.

2.3.2 Second Half-Cycle

$$\begin{aligned}\varphi_2(t) &= \mathcal{L}^{-1} [\Phi_1(s) + \Phi_2(s)] \\ \Phi_2(s) &= -\varphi_0 \frac{\Omega}{s(s+\Omega)} e^{-dT s}\end{aligned}\tag{17}$$

$$\therefore \mathcal{L}^{-1} \Phi_2(s) = -[1 - e^{-\Omega(t-dT)}] \sigma(t - dT)$$

$$\varphi_2(t) = \varphi_0 (1 - C_2 e^{-\Omega t}) \sigma(t) - \varphi_0 [1 - e^{-\Omega(t-dT)}] \sigma(t - dT)\tag{18}$$

Again, rearranging terms,

$$\varphi_2(t) = \varphi_0 [\sigma(t) - \sigma(t - dT)] + \varphi_0 [e^{-\Omega(t-dT)} \sigma(t - dT) - C_2 e^{-\Omega t} \sigma(t)]\tag{19}$$

We observe that due to the presence of $\sigma(t - dT)$ in the equation above, this contribution to the signal $\varphi_2(t)$ occurs only for $t \geq dT$, that is, during the 2^{nd} half-cycle.

For $t \geq dT$, the first term $\varphi_0 [\sigma(t) - \sigma(t - dT)] = 0$, $\sigma(t) = 1$ and $\sigma(t - dT) = 1$. The remaining (right hand) term,

$$\begin{aligned}\varphi_2(t) &= \varphi_0 [e^{-\Omega(t-dT)} - C_2 e^{-\Omega t}] \sigma(t - dT) \\ \varphi_2(t) &= \varphi_0 \left[e^{-\Omega(t-dT)} - \frac{e^{d\Omega T}}{e^{d\Omega T}} C_2 e^{-\Omega t} \right] \sigma(t - dT) \\ &= \varphi_0 \left[e^{-\Omega(t-dT)} - \frac{C_2}{e^{d\Omega T}} e^{-\Omega(t-dT)} \right] \sigma(t - dT)\end{aligned}$$

Factoring out $e^{-\Omega(t-dT)}$,

$$\varphi_2(t) = \varphi_0 (1 - C_2 e^{-d\Omega T}) e^{-\Omega(t-dT)} \sigma(t - dT) \quad (20)$$

$$\text{But } C_2 = \frac{1 - e^{-(1-d)\Omega T}}{1 - e^{-\Omega T}}, \text{ so}$$

$$1 - C_2 e^{-d\Omega T} = \frac{1 - e^{-d\Omega T}}{1 - e^{-\Omega T}} \quad (21)$$

$$\varphi_2(t) = \varphi_0 \left(\frac{1 - e^{-d\Omega T}}{1 - e^{-\Omega T}} \right) e^{-\Omega(t-dT)} \sigma(t - dT)$$

Note the negative exponent in the denominator. If we change this exponent to be a positive exponent, then

$$\frac{e^{\Omega T}}{e^{\Omega T}} \frac{1 - e^{-d\Omega T}}{1 - e^{-\Omega T}} = - \frac{e^{\Omega T} - e^{(1-d)\Omega T}}{1 - e^{\Omega T}}$$

We define

$$C_3 \stackrel{D}{=} \frac{1 - e^{-d\Omega T}}{1 - e^{-\Omega T}} = - \frac{e^{\Omega T} - e^{(1-d)\Omega T}}{1 - e^{\Omega T}} \quad (22)$$

Note: If $d = 0.5$, then $C_3 = C_2$.

$$\therefore \boxed{\varphi_2(t) = \varphi_0 C_3 e^{-\Omega(t-dT)} \sigma(t - dT)} \quad (23)$$

In summary,

$$\boxed{\varphi(t) = \begin{cases} \varphi_1(t) = \varphi_0 (1 - C_2 e^{-\Omega t}) \sigma(t) & , t < dT \\ \varphi_2(t) = \varphi_0 C_3 e^{-\Omega(t-dT)} \sigma(t - dT) & , t \geq dT \end{cases}} \quad (24)$$

3 Bipolar SquareWave Driving a Low-Pass Filter

Figure 2: A Symmetric Bipolar Square-wave

In this section of the paper we consider two methods for derivation of the equations that provide the *steady state* response (the output) of a 1st order low-pass filter excited by a symmetric bipolar square-wave.

Let $\varphi(t)$ be a periodic (bipolar, i.e., A.C.) square-wave of voltage amplitude φ_0 and duty cycle $d = \frac{t_{HI}}{t_{HI} + t_{LO}} = \frac{t_{HI}}{T}$ that switches between $+\varphi_0$ and $-\varphi_0$. The period of the square-wave is T .

The First Method.

We have already considered the unipolar square-wave. We can extend the results of those derivations to bipolar square-waves.

We accomplish this by a simple replacement operation: $\varphi(t) \leftarrow 2\varphi(t) - \varphi_0$.

$$\varphi_1(t) \leftarrow 2\varphi_0 (1 - C_2 e^{-\Omega t}) \sigma(t) - \varphi_0 \Rightarrow \varphi_1(t) = \varphi_0 (1 - 2C_2 e^{-\Omega t}) \sigma(t)$$

$$\varphi_2(t) \leftarrow 2\varphi_0 [C_3 e^{-\Omega(t-dT)}] \sigma(t-dT) - \varphi_0 \Rightarrow \varphi_2(t) = \varphi_0 (-1 + 2C_3 e^{-\Omega(t-dT)}) \sigma(t-dT)$$

So,

$$\varphi(t) = \begin{cases} \varphi_1(t) = \varphi_0 (1 - 2C_2 e^{-\Omega t}) \sigma(t) & , t < dT \\ \varphi_2(t) = \varphi_0 [-1 + 2C_3 e^{-\Omega(t-dT)}] \sigma(t-dT) & , t \geq dT \end{cases} \quad (25)$$

The Second Method.

For Example.

A bipolar square-wave voltage φ drives a coil of constant inductance L in series with a resistor R . This coil might be the primary coil of a magnetic flux-gate in series with a (current limiting) resistor R . $\varphi = \varphi_0 f(t)$, where φ_0 is the voltage amplitude and $f(t)$ is a bipolar symmetric square-wave of amplitude 1. $\mathcal{L} f(t) = F(s)$.

$\Phi_o(s) = \mathcal{L}(\varphi(t)) = \mathcal{L}[\varphi_0 f(t)] = \varphi_0 \mathcal{L} f(t) = \varphi_0 F(s)$. $\varphi_0 F(s)$ is the Laplace transform of the bipolar square-wave voltage input into the low-pass filter $LPF1$.

The transfer function of the current through the resistor and coil is:

$i_o(t) = \frac{\varphi}{R} LPF1(\tau)$, in which $LPF1(\tau) = \frac{1}{\tau D + 1}$ is a 1st order low-pass filter and $D = \frac{d}{dt}$ is the differential operator. $i_o(t) = \frac{\varphi}{R} \frac{1}{\tau D + 1}$ and $\tau = \frac{L}{R}$ is the system time constant. $\Omega = \frac{1}{\tau}$.

First, consider the *first cycle* of the bipolar square-wave which waveform must be replicated:

$$f_0(t) = \sigma(t) - 2\sigma(t - dT) + \sigma(t - T)$$

The complete square-wave for all cycles is $f(t) = \sum f_0(t)$; that is,

$$f(t) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} [\sigma(t - kT) - 2\sigma[t - (k + d)T] + \sigma(t - (k + 1)T)] \quad (26)$$

$$\text{that is, } f(t) = \begin{cases} +1, & t \in [kT, (k + d)T) \\ -1, & t \in [(k + d)T, kT) \end{cases}, \text{ integer } k \in [0, \infty)$$

$$F(s) = \mathcal{L} f(t) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{s} [e^{-kTs} - 2e^{-(k+d)Ts} + e^{-(k+1)Ts}]$$

$$\Phi_o(s) = \varphi_0 F(s) = \varphi_0 \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{s} [e^{-kTs} - 2e^{-(k+d)Ts} + e^{-(k+1)Ts}] \quad (27)$$

$$\Phi_o(s) = \varphi_0 \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{e^{-kTs}}{s} (1 - 2e^{-dT} + e^{-Ts})$$

$$\Phi_o(s) = \frac{\varphi_0}{s} (1 - 2e^{-dT} + e^{-Ts}) \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} e^{-kTs}$$

But

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} e^{-kTs} = \frac{1}{1 - e^{-Ts}}, \text{ so } \boxed{\Phi_o(s) = \frac{\varphi_0}{s} \frac{1 - 2e^{-dT} + e^{-Ts}}{1 - e^{-Ts}}} \quad (28)$$

With $\varphi = \varphi_0 f(t)$, the output of the low-pass filter $LPF1$ is

$$i_o(t) = \frac{\varphi}{R} LPF1(\tau) = \frac{\varphi}{R} \frac{1}{\tau D + 1} = \frac{\varphi_0}{R} f(t) \frac{1}{\tau D + 1}$$

$$I_o(s) = \mathcal{L} i_o(t) = \frac{\varphi_0}{R} F(s) \frac{1}{\tau s + 1} = \frac{1}{R} \Phi_o(s) \frac{1}{\tau s + 1} = \frac{1}{R} \Phi_o(s) \frac{\Omega}{s + \Omega}, \text{ so}$$

$$\boxed{I_o(s) = \mathcal{L} i_o(t) = \frac{\varphi_0}{R} \frac{\Omega}{s(s + \Omega)} \frac{1 - 2e^{-dT_s} + e^{-Ts}}{1 - e^{-Ts}}} \quad (29)$$

in which $\tau = \frac{L}{R}$ and $\Omega = \frac{1}{\tau}$. As in our treatment of the unipolar square-wave, we repeat: This is the *complete* solution to the first order ordinary differential equation. We may then determine $i_o(t) = \mathcal{L}^{-1}I_o(s)$. Since we are interested in the steady state response of the output of *LPF1*, we will subtract the transient solution from it.

The *repetition operator* is $RPT(s) = \frac{1}{1 - e^{-Ts}}$, and it represents infinite series replication.

$I_o(s) = I_t(s) + I(s)$ in which $I_o(s)$ is the complete solution Laplace transform,

$I_t(s)$ is the transient Laplace transform and $I(s)$ is the steady state Laplace transform.

3.1 Removing the Transient Term

There is a pole at $s = -\Omega = -\frac{1}{\tau}$. To obtain the transient term, we replace every occurrence of s by $-\Omega$ in the complete solution except in the *LPF1* transport function term $\frac{\Omega}{s + \Omega}$. Thus,

$$I_t(s) = \frac{\varphi_0}{R} \frac{\Omega}{(-\Omega)(s + \Omega)} \frac{1 - 2e^{d\Omega T} + e^{\Omega T}}{1 - e^{\Omega T}} \quad (30)$$

To make our algebra less cumbersome, define

$$C_4 \stackrel{D}{=} \frac{1 - 2e^{d\Omega T} + e^{\Omega T}}{1 - e^{\Omega T}} \quad (31)$$

$$I_t(s) = -\frac{\varphi_0}{R} \frac{1}{(s + \Omega)} C_4$$

Notice the change in signs, minus $\leftarrow$ plus, in the exponents.

Upon completion of our derivations, we shall have no more need of this constant.

$$I(s) = I_o(s) - I_t(s) \Rightarrow$$

$$I(s) = \frac{\varphi_0}{R} \frac{\Omega}{s(s + \Omega)} \frac{1 - 2e^{-dT_s} + e^{-Ts}}{1 - e^{-Ts}} - \left(-\frac{\varphi_0}{R} \frac{1}{s + \Omega} C_4 \right)$$

3.2 Removing the Periodic Replication

Now perform the replacements $1 - e^{-Ts} \leftarrow 1$ and $e^{-Ts} \leftarrow 0$ as we did in the section on unipolar square-waves:

$$I(s) = \frac{\varphi_0}{R} \frac{\Omega}{s(s+\Omega)} (1 - 2e^{-dT s}) + \frac{\varphi_0}{R} \frac{1}{s+\Omega} C_4 \quad (32)$$

Rearranging terms, the complete one-cycle steady state response of the system is...

$$I(s) = \frac{\varphi_0}{R} \left[\frac{\Omega}{s(s+\Omega)} \left(1 + \frac{s}{\Omega} C_4 \right) - \frac{2\Omega}{s(s+\Omega)} e^{-dT s} \right] = I_1(s) + I_2(s) \quad (33)$$

$$\boxed{I(s) = \frac{\varphi_0}{R} \frac{\Omega}{s(s+\Omega)} \left[\left(1 + \frac{s}{\Omega} C_4 \right) - 2 e^{-dT s} \right] = I_1(s) + I_2(s)} \quad (34)$$

wherein which

$$I_1(s) = \frac{\varphi_0}{R} \left[\frac{\Omega}{s(s+\Omega)} \left(1 + \frac{s}{\Omega} C_4 \right) \right] \quad (35)$$

and

$$I_2(s) = -\frac{\varphi_0}{R} \frac{2\Omega}{s(s+\Omega)} e^{-dT s} \quad (36)$$

As we shall see after obtaining the inverse Laplace transforms of these two equations, $\Phi_1(s)$ is the system response during $t < dT$ due to the 1st half-cycle of excitation, and

$I_2(s)$ is the *additional* system response during $t \geq dT$ due to the 2nd half-cycle of excitation. That is, this 2nd half-cycle excitation $I_2(s)$ is augmented by the sustained contribution of response from the 1st half-cycle which persists into the 2nd half-cycle. Thus, the system response during $t \geq dT$ is $I_1(s) + I_2(s)$.

We now determine, step by step, the inverse Laplace transform of each of these two terms.

3.2.1 First Half-Cycle

$$i_1(t) = \frac{\varphi_0}{R} \mathcal{L}^{-1} \left[\frac{\Omega}{s(s+\Omega)} + \frac{1}{s+\Omega} C_4 \right] \quad (37)$$

$$i_1(t) = \frac{\varphi_0}{R} \mathcal{L}^{-1} \frac{\Omega}{s(s+\Omega)} + \frac{\varphi_0}{R} C_4 \mathcal{L}^{-1} \frac{1}{s+\Omega}$$

$$i_1(t) = \frac{\varphi_0}{R} [\sigma(t) - e^{-\Omega t}] + \frac{\varphi_0}{R} C_4 e^{-\Omega t} \quad (38)$$

$$i_1(t) = \frac{\varphi_0}{R} [\sigma(t) - e^{-\Omega t} + C_4 e^{-\Omega t}] \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma(t) = 1$$

Rewriting this as

$$i_1(t) = \frac{\varphi_0}{R} [1 - (1 - C_4) e^{-\Omega t}]$$

and noting that

$$1 - C_4 = 2 C_2 \tag{39}$$

$$\boxed{\therefore i_1(t) = \frac{\varphi_0}{R} (1 - 2 C_2 e^{-\Omega t}) \sigma(t)} \tag{40}$$

We observe that due to the presence of $\sigma(t)$ in the $\varphi_1(t)$ equation above, the signal $\varphi_1(t)$ persists into the the 2^{nd} half-cycle.

3.2.2 Second Half-Cycle

$$i_2(t) = i_1(t) + \mathcal{L}^{-1} \left[-\frac{\varphi_0}{R} \frac{2\Omega}{s(s+\Omega)} e^{-dT s} \right] = i_1(t) - \frac{2\varphi_0}{R} \mathcal{L}^{-1} \left[\frac{\Omega}{s(s+\Omega)} e^{-dT s} \right]$$

$$i_2(t) = \frac{\varphi_0}{R} (1 - 2 C_2 e^{-\Omega t}) - \frac{2\varphi_0}{R} [1 - e^{-\Omega(t-dT)}] \sigma(t - dT) \tag{41}$$

$$i_2(t) = \frac{\varphi_0}{R} [1 - 2 C_2 e^{-\Omega t} - 2 + 2 e^{-\Omega(t-dT)}] \sigma(t - dT)$$

$$i_2(t) = \frac{\varphi_0}{R} [-1 + 2 e^{-\Omega(t-dT)} - 2 C_2 e^{-\Omega t}] \sigma(t - dT)$$

$$i_2(t) = \frac{\varphi_0}{R} [-1 + 2 (e^{-\Omega(t-dT)} - C_2 e^{-\Omega t})] \sigma(t - dT)$$

$$i_2(t) = \frac{\varphi_0}{R} \left[-1 + 2 \left(-e^{-\Omega(t-dT)} - C_2 \frac{e^{\Omega dT}}{e^{d\Omega dT}} e^{-\Omega t} \right) \right] \sigma(t - dT)$$

$$i_2(t) = \frac{\varphi_0}{R} [-1 + 2 (1 - C_2 e^{-\Omega dT}) e^{-\Omega(t-dT)}] \sigma(t - dT)$$

$$\text{But } 1 - C_2 e^{-\Omega dT} = C_3 \tag{42}$$

$$\therefore \boxed{i_2(t) = \frac{\varphi_0}{R} [-1 + 2 C_3 e^{-\Omega(t-dT)}] \sigma(t - dT)} \tag{43}$$

We observe that due to the presence of $\sigma(t - dT)$ in the equation above, this contribution to the signal $\varphi_2(t)$ occurs only for $t \geq dT$, that is, during the 2nd half-cycle.

Thus,

$$\varphi(t) = \begin{cases} \varphi_1(t) = \varphi_0 (1 - 2C_2 e^{-\Omega t}) \sigma(t) & , \quad t < dT \\ \varphi_2(t) = \varphi_0 [-1 + 2C_3 e^{-\Omega(t-dT)}] \sigma(t - dT) & , \quad t \geq dT \end{cases} \quad (44)$$

These equations are the same as those obtained via the first method, as indeed they must be. They are the unique solutions to a differential equation.

Repeating, with attention focused on the signs ($\pm$) of the exponents,

$$\begin{aligned} C_1 &= \frac{1 - e^{d\Omega T}}{1 - e^{\Omega T}} = -\frac{e^{-\Omega T} - e^{-(1-d)\Omega T}}{1 - e^{-\Omega T}} \\ C_2 &= -\frac{e^{\Omega T} - e^{d\Omega T}}{1 - e^{\Omega T}} = \frac{1 - e^{-(1-d)\Omega T}}{1 - e^{-\Omega T}} \\ C_3 &= -\frac{e^{\Omega T} - e^{(1-d)\Omega T}}{1 - e^{\Omega T}} = \frac{1 - e^{-d\Omega T}}{1 - e^{-\Omega T}} \\ C_4 &= \frac{1 - 2e^{d\Omega T} + e^{\Omega T}}{1 - e^{\Omega T}} \\ C_1 + C_2 &= 1, \quad 1 + C_4 = 2C_1, \quad 1 - C_4 = 2C_2 \\ C_1 - C_2 &= C_4, \quad C_1 > 0, \quad C_2 > 0, \quad C_3 > 0 \end{aligned}$$

■ End